

transceivers there has been a steady increase in their usage in access/metro scenarios with so called whiteboxes [7] and much attention has been given to their integration in control planes for service provisioning. A common management interface to configure the pluggables is the Optical Internetworking Forum (OIF) common management interface specification (CMIS) [8], which includes extensions for coherent modules. A common approach is to deploy a NETCONF OpenConfig SDN agent that maps configuration and control of central frequency, output power and operational modes to CMIS operations. In the context of the IETF, initial efforts such as [9] addresses the modelling of an optical pluggable within a host packet device in context of a packet over optical network, jointly addressing photonic/optical attributes, host/electrical attributes, and physical and functional aspects, in the areas of capabilities, profiles, configuration, state and performance monitoring. From the point of network control and management, IPoWDM eliminates the need for transponders/muxponders and grey interfaces but raises the issue of control between the IP and optical domains. This problem has been addressed from multiple aspects (see Fig.1, cfr. [10-11] and the references within). These include initial assessments, demonstrations and comparison of control plane scenarios, highlighting trade-offs in terms of workflow complexity or avoiding issues related to multiple controllers modifying the same device conflicts and loss of database consistency.

Architectures within TIP MANTRA and IETF

This problem and initial architectures have been formalized within the Telecom Infra Project (TIP), MANTRA (metaverse ready architectures for open transport) group [12] with distinct SDN architectures (Dual and Single SBI). Both solutions allow only the IP controller to configure IPoWDM nodes; however, in the Dual solution

the optical controller is allowed to read the current configuration of optical pluggables. An initial demonstration of the MANTRA single architecture was provided in [13] demonstrating the setup of a point-to-point connectivity service and characterizing the 400 ZR/ZR+ coherent pluggable transceivers in terms of tunability. Related efforts are addressed at the IETF: [14] provides general overarching guidelines for control and management of packet over optical converged networks with programmable pluggables and focuses on operators' use cases and [15] proposed an additional approach for control of optical pluggables providing the direct read/write access of coherent plugs to the optical controller, thereby allowing the end-to-end management.

Linux Foundation Transport API

The Open Network Modeling and Interfaces (ONMI) TAPI project is responsible for the development of an SDK as an Open-Source project. It abstracts a common set of control plane functions such as network topology, connectivity, path computation or OAM a set of Service interfaces.

This paper focuses on the photonic media layer: models the OTSi/OTSiA/OTSiG, Media Channels (NMC/MC/MCA) and OMS, OTS layers as per [16] using a unified set of protocol layer qualifiers. TAPI is based on a *context* relationship between a server and client, an abstraction that allows for logical isolation and grouping of network resource abstractions for specific purposes/applications and/or information exchange. The context includes: i) the set of Service Interface Points (SIPs) exposed to the TAPI client applications representing customer-facing access points for requesting network services; ii) a *topology-context* which includes one or more top-level Topology objects; iii) a *connectivity-context* which includes the list of connectivity services and connection objects. From a topological point of view

Figure 2: Scenario showing an OTSiMC connectivity between add/drop ports corresponding to the Optical Line System

the TAPI Topology is an abstract representation of the topological aspects. It is described in terms of the underlying topological network of nodes and links. Nodes are an abstract representation of the forwarding-capabilities of a particular set of network resources, described in terms of the aggregation of set of ports (Node-Edge-Point, or NEP) and the potential to enable forwarding of information between those edge ports. Links is a topological entity which is an abstract representation of the effective adjacency between two or more nodes. On the other hand, a logical termination points (LTP) is a generalized representation of termination and adaptation functions and realized by four different TAPI constructs: Service-Interface-Point (SIP), Connectivity Service-End-Point (CSEP) Node-Edge-Point (NEP) and Connection-End-Point (CEP) and they can model different technology layers, different network configurations or capabilities. The CEP represents capacity and functionality used, at a particular point in the network to directly support a connection, covering termination, and adaptation, having client-server relationship with the Node-Edge-Point. The TAPI Connectivity-Service represents a request for connectivity between two or more Service-Interface-Points and the Connection represents an enabled (provisioned) forwarding capability between two or more CEPs, tracking the state of the allocated resources, mostly considering cross-connections (XC) – defined as a connection between Connection-End-Points of the same layer within a node that cannot be further decomposed and Top Connections, which represents connectivity at the highest level of partition.

Connectivity Models

The RIA specifies in detail common scenarios including, for example, partial disaggregation

(Fig.2) or Integrated management (Fig.3). It shows scenario at “time zero”, i.e., the model of logical resources made available by the server controller before any provisioning is performed by client controller, followed by examples of the possible provisioning scenarios.

P2MP DSCM pluggables

P2MP coherent optics based on digital subcarrier multiplexing (DSCM) [17] has the potential to provide connectivity in access, aggregation and metropolitan networks at a low cost, using DSCM to split the bandwidth into multiple Nyquist digital subcarriers (SCs) at a lower symbol rate. Each SC can be treated independently and routed to different destinations, allowing a greater degree of flexibility. The P2MP pluggables implement a dual management interface as described in [18]. The Optical Network is thus able to process user requests for P2P and P2MP services at the DSR level e.g., delegating the configuration of the pluggables to a dedicated controller (the XR Intelligent Pluggable Manager or IPM) and the configuration of the optical line to a dedicated OLS controller. The workflow includes computes the nominal central frequency for the DSCM and requests the creation of an XR network or constellation to the IPM; configuring the optical line system as needed; and driving the creation of the service between the Ethernet ports in the router available breakouts, e.g. adding leaves to the XR network selecting the leaf modules.

Conclusion

This tutorial has provided an overview of the challenges and solutions related to the IPoD-WDM control, including coherent pluggables, and the role of TAPI as a standard NBI in the different architectures.

Figure 3: Scenario showing an OTSiMC connectivity between add/drop ports corresponding to the Integrated Control

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